

The Anodic Passivation of Zinc in Alkaline Solutions

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Galvanostatic studies have been made on the anodic passivation of zinc in alkaline solutions. The influence of the current density, concentration of the alkali saturated with zinc oxide and the purity of the electrode metal on the behaviour of anodic passivation have been studied. Pure zinc (proanalyse, Merck) electrode does not show the passivation tendency upto very high current densities, contrary to commercial pure zinc electrode which exhibits the changes in its potential in positive direction even at very low current densities. Potential versus time, potential versus passivating current density curves were obtained.

The results obtained on the passivation of zinc in alkaline solutions have been discussed here. Equation relating the limiting current densities of necessary to passivate the metal is found to be directly proportional to the square of the concentration of hydroxyl ions. The experimental results indicate that the passivation tendency of zinc is least within a concentration range of 6N to 10N KOH. From the potential-passivation current curve it has been pointed out that the commercially pure zinc passivates in three discrete stages which correspond to the local cell action, anodic dissolution of the metal and the passivation of the electrode followed by the evolution of oxygen. The nature of the deep blue colour film obtained on the surface of pure zinc electrode when the later is being subjected to the anodic treatment has been discussed.

Since the early thirties of the present century considerable amount of work has been done on the anodic passivation of zinc by a number of workers notably Newbery¹, Muller², Clark and Akimov³, Beieri⁴, Laake⁵, Dirkse⁶, Wakkad, Shams El Din and Kolb⁷, Sanghi and Wynne Jones⁸, Sanghi and Fleischmann⁹, Eisenberg, Bauman and Brettner¹⁰, and Hampson and Tarbox¹¹. The investigations were made on the growth, composition, physical properties such as thickness, resistivity, colour etc., of the insoluble film formed, on the changes in potentials and current in relation to the growth of the film, and also on the current time relationships developed by Muller², Shutt and Walton¹², and Armstrong and Butler¹³. Although, these researches have thrown much light on various aspects of anodic passivation of zinc, they appear to lack in detail in giving a chronological account of the phenomenon occurring at the electrode and in explaining the mecha-

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nism of anodic passivation of the metals of the second kind like zinc which give the anodic reaction products soluble to a considerable extent in the electrolyte. In the present paper the authors have reported the galvanostatic studies on the anodic passivation of zinc; the influences of the current density, concentration of the electrolyte and the purity of the electrode metal on the behaviour of anodic passivation of zinc have been investigated. The mechanism of the phenomenon of anodic passivation of metals of second kind is explained.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental set-up consisted of a set of 90V batteries along with a variable and fixed resistances as the source of constant current, an I shape zinc rod of 0.289 cm² exposed as the experimental electrode, 6.25 cm² platinum foil attached firmly to a thick platinum wire as the auxiliary electrode (cathode) and a pyrex glass vessel of 7 cm. diameter and 6 cm. height as the cell. Mercury/mercuric oxide-IN. KOH half cell was used as a reference electrode for the measurement of the potentials of zinc electrode. The potential measurements are made with Rohde and Schwarz., URI Meter. All the experiments were performed at room temperature and under unstirred conditions. The circuit diagram is given in figure 1.

Fig. 1: Circuit diagram for galvanostatic studies on passivation. A: Ammeter; B: H.T. Battery; C: Cell; E: Experimental Electrode; R: Reference Electrode; S: Band Switch.

Fig. 2A. Polarisation curves for commercially pure zinc in N KOH.

The polarisation experiments were carried out over a wide range of currents. Within a range of 3 mA to 15 mA, currents were drawn from a single 90V battery through suitable variable and fixed resistances contacted by means of band switches. Higher currents—15 to 60 mA—were tapped from a set of three 90V batteries connected in parallel. The current remained steady throughout the course of experiments. In some cases little adjustment of current was needed just after the electrode became passive.

In each experiment a fresh 150 ml. solution of potassium hydroxide (Analar, BDH) either pure or saturated with zinc oxide (Analar, Merck quality)—as the case might be—was taken in the pyrex cell. No attempt was made to avoid the adsorption of atmospheric carbon dioxide by the solution during the course of the experiment, that is for a period not longer than 150 minutes.

The end face of the horizontal limb of L shape zinc electrode alone was subjected to passivation and the remaining surface of the electrode was stopped off by Casein (BDH) or paraffin wax (pure BDH).

The exposed surface of the zinc electrode was polished successively on various grades of emery papers (0 to 410) lubricated by alcohol. Anode and cathode were placed 4 cm. apart in the cell. The luggin capillary of the reference electrode was kept very close to the surface of zinc electrode.

In the present investigations an attempt has been made to perform experiments under the conditions which are not much different from the conditions often met with in many practical problems where zinc/zinc oxide—KOH system is being used as an electrode, such as, in silver oxide zinc batteries, Ruben cells etc., the results obtained in these fundamental investigations may therefore be of direct applications to these problems.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The passivation of zinc has been found to be largely influenced by factors such as (a) the purity of the metal; (b) concentration of the electrolyte; (c) saturation of alkali solution with zinc oxide; and (d) current density. There are a number of other factors which may also influence the passivation e.g., (a) the annealing which eliminates stresses in a metal; (b) temperature and (c) the traces of carbon dioxide being adsorbed from the atmosphere. These factors may however be of secondary nature as they influence the phenomenon of passivation to a smaller degree only. A few preliminary experiments were carried out on these secondary factors; the first two were found to affect the anodic processes to a noticeable extent at low current density range viz., 0 to 100 mA/cm². The atmospheric carbon dioxide does not seem to influence the anodic polarization in potassium hydroxide solution during the period of experimentation probably because of the high concentration of potassium hydroxide electrolyte in the solution. The experiments at low current densities have been carried out in an air conditioned room.

Fig. 2B: Polarisation curves for pure zinc in N KOH.

Potential-Time curves: Experiments are carried out on the polarisation of analytical and commercial grade zinc metal in various concentrations of potassium hydroxide solution at different current densities. The potential time curves for the two grades of the metal in 1N KOH solution are given in figures 2A and 2B. The curves differ markedly in the following aspects.

The initial rest potential of commercially pure grade zinc in 1N KOH solution was $-0.82V$ with respect to $Hg/HgO-1N$ KOH. The electrode potential showed a continuous rise in 1N KOH solution at all the anodic current densities right from zero. The rate of change in potential became faster greater the current density (fig. 2A) and beyond 10 mA/cm^2 current density, the electrode instantaneously attained the maximum potential. The initial rest potential in concentrated solutions, was much more negative than $-0.8V$ and the rate of change in potential was much slower. The peak potential values corresponding to the minimum current density just sufficient to passivate the commercially pure zinc metal in nearly 120 minutes are listed in table I.

TABLE I
Anodic Polarisation of Commercially Pure Grade Zinc in KOH Saturated with ZnO .

Current density— mA/cm^2 sq.	Peak potential attained in 120 minutes (Volts)
Zero	-0.35
0.04	0.95
0.40	1.05
2.61	1.52
3.44	1.59
4.55	1.8
7.01	3.4
7.60	5.0
12.14	5.75
16.19	6.05
24.29	6.5
40.47	6.7

The initial rest potential of AR grade zinc in 1N KOH solution was $-1.32V$ which is close to the reversible potential of $Zn/Zn(OH)_2$ system. The electrode potential did not show any sign of change in 150 minutes, from the initial rest potential even at fairly high current densities. Beyond 10 mA/cm^2 current densities the potential of the electrode, changed slowly from $-1.32V$ to $-1.15V$ and then rose instantaneously to 2.2V to 2.5V. In table II, the values for the current and passivation time are given for pure zinc electrode polarised in various concentrations of potassium hydroxide solution.

The marked difference between the values of passivation potentials for impure and pure zinc electrodes in 1N KOH solution may be noted.

Current-potential Curves: From potential-time curves given in figure 2A, it may be noted that the maximum polarisation potential attained by the impure zinc electrode is a function of the current density used in the experiments. In the lowest current density range (0 to 12 mA/cm^2) the electrode potential tends towards more positive values with respect to its initial rest potential $-0.8V$, however it retains its negative sign. The maxima of polarisation potentials are plotted against the current densities in figures 3A and 3B. The curves clearly show that anodic polarisation of impure zinc which at high

current densities leads to its passivation occurs in several stages each of which differs from one another in its nature.

TABLE II
Variation of Time of Passivation with Current Density of Pure Zinc Metal Electrode

Electrolyte	Current density mA/cm. sq.	Time of passivation Minutes
N KOH	10.36	149.0
	12.1	112.5
	13.62	105.0
	17.28	60.0
	22.46	28.0
	27.65	16.5
	34.55	2.0
N KOH SATURATED WITH ZINC OXIDE	13.82	64.0
	20.73	20.0
	27.65	10.0
	29.37	2.0
2N KOH SATURATED WITH ZINC OXIDE	41.7	98.0
	62.2	36.0
	86.38	8.5
	91.56	3.5
4N KOH SATURATED WITH ZINC OXIDE	103.6	75.0
	138.2	21.0
	155.5	13.0
	172.8	7.5
	190.1	4.75
6N KOH SATURATED WITH ZINC OXIDE	172.8	12.5
	190.1	7.5
	207.3	2.5
8N KOH SATURATED WITH ZINC OXIDE	110.4	85.0
	123.6	41.0
	132.4	25.0
	176.6	2.5
	183.1	2.5

Concentration-Current Density Curve: The current densities necessary to passivate zinc within a definite time seems to be influenced by the concentration of the electrolyte. Fixing the passivation time limits as 3.5 ± 1.5 minutes, detailed investigations are made to determine the current densities necessary to passivate the pure zinc electrode over a wide range of concentrations—1N to 16N of KOH solution. The data are plotted in figure 4. The parabolic curve obtained for concentration versus current density shows that high current densities are needed to passivate the zinc electrode in the range of 6N to 10N potassium hydroxide solutions. This means that zinc has least tendency for passivation within 6N to 10N concentrations and largest in low (1N) as well as very high (16N) concentrations of the alkaline solutions.

DISCUSSION

The mechanism of anodic passivation of metals has been discussed by Muller and later by several other workers with reference to gold and nickel in particular. The basic picture of passivation of a metal oxide film on the surface of the metal, still stands but with a few modifications⁴.

Fig. 3A: Limiting Potential Vs Current Density (upto 1.4 mA/cm²) curve for impure Zinc in N KOH.

Fig. 3B: Limiting Potential Vs Current Density (>1.4 mA/cm²) curve for impure zinc in N KOH.

As stated earlier the anodic behaviour of zinc is profoundly influenced by the purity of the metal. The A. R. grade zinc metal electrode does not show a rise in potential over a very wide range of current densities 0 to 10 mA/cm² (Fig. 2) while the potential of C.P. grade zinc rises continuously in the positive direction in absence as well as in presence of impressed anodic currents, (Fig. 1). Polarisation of anodes and cathodes is due to the hydrogen evolution and oxygen reduction reactions at impurity centres only. The impurity atoms and the zinc atoms in the commercially pure zinc may act as cathodic and anodic centres respectively and thus form local cells in contact with the solution. The metal thus corrodes and the potential rises slowly upto nearly -0.6V in 120 minutes. On impressing higher and higher anodic currents on the electrode, the electrode potential tends towards more positive values owing to the polarisation of anodic areas on the surface. The process of anodic dissolution supported by local cell action in the case of C.P. grade zinc thus continue upto a stage where all the anodic areas on the metal surface are completely polarised. The limiting current density 3.7 mA/cm² corresponding to the first inflection point 'd' in the curve given in Fig. 3 (B) corresponds to the completion of polarisation of the anodic area. On the other hand, this phenomenon does not occur in A.R. grade zinc metal owing to the absence of the cathodic impurities. Because of the absence of local cell action no inflection is noticed in the curve of A.R. grade zinc in the region of low current density. The second and third inflections ce and eg in potential current curve (Fig. 3(B) indicate the changes in the nature of the anodic process. The influence of local cell action at higher current density (>2.7 mA/cm²) becomes less significant and the anodic dissolution process predominates. A definite concentration of zincate ions is built up in the vicinity of the electrode at the current densities lying between 2.7 mA/cm² to 4 mA/cm² and the electrode potential tends towards the reversible positive potential value of the Zn/ZnO₂²⁻ system. The inflection C thus signifies to the attainment of the reversible potential by the electrode as a result of the accelerated rate of anodic dissolution of zinc and building up of zincate ions pool in the vicinity of the electrode under unstirred conditions. Further

increase in current upto nearly 10mA/cm² does not show any appreciable change in the electrode potential.

Pourbaix¹⁴ and coworkers have obtained potential — pH diagram for zinc. The diagram indicates the pH ranges within which various products of anodic reactions can be obtained.

Zinc readily corrodes and produces free zinc ions in acidic pH, sparingly soluble zinc hydroxide in solutions around neutrality (8.5 to 12 pH) and soluble zincate ions in strong alkali solutions. Beyond 10 mA/cm² anodic current density, zinc corrodes at such fast rates that the pH of the solution falls considerably in the vicinity of the electrode owing to the depletion of the hydroxyl ions and the formation of zincate ions. The sparingly soluble hydroxide is thrown out of the solution the moment the ionic product of zinc and hydroxyl ions exceeds the solubility product of the former; at this stage a stable film of zinc oxide which does not dissolve in low alkaline pH range covers the electrode surface rendering the latter passive and retards the process of anodic dissolution and facilitates the evolution of oxygen at the surface of the anode. Thus, inflection *fg* obtained in potential—current curve (Fig. 3B) represents the change in the anodic reaction viz., the formation of insoluble film on the electrode. It is thus seen that commercially pure grade zinc undergoes anodic polarisation in three distinct stages under unstirred condition. The first stage is predominated by the local cell action, second mainly by the anodic dissolution of the metal and third by the passivation followed by the evolution of oxygen.

Fig. 4: Curve for the limiting passivation current densities corresponding to a fixed passivation time 3.5 ± 1.3 minutes for the pure zinc electrode obtained in various concentrations of KOH solution.

Anodic passivation of zinc is controlled by the reaction,

For the above reaction

where K is a constant. The concentration of the zincate ions in the alkali solution is proportional to the square of the concentration of hydroxyl ions. Evidently definite concentrations of zincate ions will exist in the solution for each concentration of the potassium hydroxide. According to the equation (4), the concentration of zincate ions in the bulk of the solution would increase with the increase of hydroxyl ion concentration. However, the ionic product of potassium and zincate ions may not exceed the limiting solubility of potassium zincate ion in the vicinity of the electrode owing to the crystallisation in spite of continuous increase in hydroxyl ion concentration.

If the equilibrium concentration of zincate ions is expressed with reference to its limiting maximum concentration say ' b ' g. mole/litre in the vicinity of the electrode surface and that of hydroxyl ion concentration is expressed with reference to its concentration ' a ' at which the corresponding concentration of zincate ions is its limiting concentration ' b '; the equation (5) will take up the following form in the region of the electrode surface where

$$(b-y) = K' (a-x)^2 \quad (6)$$

$(b-y)$ and $(a-x)$ represent the actual equilibrium concentrations of zincate and hydroxyl ions respectively, and ' x ' and ' y ' represent the shifts in the concentration of OH^- and ZnO_2^{2-} ions from their critical limiting values expressed by ' a ' and ' b ' respectively.

On impressing an anodic current on a zinc electrode, the latter would continue to dissolve without becoming passive so long the concentration of the zincate ions would not reach the critical concentration equivalent to $K'(a-x)^2$ in equation (6) in the vicinity of the electrodes. Once a critical concentration of zincate ions is reached sparingly soluble zinc hydroxide will be thrown out creating the favourable conditions for the formation of stable zinc oxide film on the anode surface. Under the unstirred conditions, when the diffusion of zincate ions in the vicinity of the anode is negligible in comparison to the rate of their production, the quantity of zincate ions produced, will be proportional to the quantity of the current, I , passed through the electrode. If the time factor ' t ' is kept constant, the quantity of the zincate ions produced will be proportional to the current density T .

Let I_0 and I be the current densities needed for the production of ' b ' and ' y ' g. mol/litre concentrations of zincate ions respectively; then the current densities difference $(I_0 - I)$ will be proportional to $(b-y)$ as well as to $(a-x)^2$. So we have a parabolic curve in current density and alkali concentration. The parabola is symmetrical about the current density axis, indicating that for each value of I there will be two definite concentration of hydroxyl ions. Thus, ' T ' will increase in the first instance with the increase in the concentration of hydroxyl ions in the solution reaching a maximum limit and then will recede with the further increase in the concentration of hydroxyl ions. Experimental results, plotted in figure 4, lie on a parabola where, $a=8$ g. mol/litre, $b=0.21$ amp/cm² and $m=0.394$ amp. lit/cm² g., confirming the present theory.

Nature of the oxide film: The films found during the course of passivation on pure and commercially pure grade zinc electrode differed markedly in appearance and adherence towards the electrode surface. First grey and subsequently greenish films are formed on both the surfaces at low current densities. The film on commercially pure grade zinc turns white, grows thicker with time and forms aggregate of a number of white layers which peel off successively from the surface beyond passivation current densities. The film on pure zinc electrode turns deep blue in colour instead of becoming a loose white mass.

after the passivation of the electrode. The blue films remain smooth, strongly adherent to the surface and grows thicker on continued polarisation.

If a few divalent zinc ions like other transitional metal ions oxidise to trivalent state, letting loose a few electrons in accordance with the following reaction:

the free electrons in the ZnO lattices may account for the 'n' type behaviour of zinc oxide crystals. The resemblance in the colour of the Zn⁺⁺⁺ and Cu⁺⁺ ions may also be attributed to the common incompleated 3d orbital structure which renders these ions paramagnetic. In the absence of detailed information about the blue of zinc oxide film, the question of its colour however remains open.